

The “High and Lifted Up” Son of Man Christology of John’s Gospel

A paper prepared for the Sixth Enoch Seminar Nangeroni Meeting on

John the Jew: Reading the Gospel of John’s Christology in Light of Jewish Messianism

Camaldoli, Italy, June 19-24, 2016¹

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Introduction.

Human intuition often suggests that Jesus, as an exalted figure, is by nature somewhere between God (the Father) and (mere) human, with the further intuition that the “higher” the Christology, the lesser should be the humanity of Jesus. The heresy of Docetism, for example, suggests that the fully divine Jesus only seemed to be a human being. Discussions of John’s Christology often focus on how “high” it is. While I concur that John’s Christology is “high,” I do not believe that it is “high-er” than elsewhere in the NT; I have maintained that the same high Christology, according to which Jesus is rightly called “YHWH the God of Israel,” runs throughout the NT; only John’s emphasis, his selection of material, and some of his terminology (especially the Logos title) is unique.² But John seems equally at pains to present the real, human nature of Jesus, beginning with his choice of the word “flesh” (σάρξ) in John 1:14, with his repeated use of ἄνθρωπος, even when it is not required by Greek grammar,³ and of his truly human experiences, whether emotions (John 11:33-35), distress at his impending suffering (John 12:27), thirst (John 19:28), physical weariness (John 4:6), etc. It would seem more appropriate to describe John’s Christology (consistent with the rest of the NT), as both “high” and “low,” with respect to his two natures. This paper focuses on the intersection between the recurring “high and lifted up” terminology found throughout Isaiah, which suggests already a savior who is both human and divine, the “lifted up” and “glorified” terminology in John’s Gospel, and the idea of the glorification of the Son of Man as the last Adam, with Psalm 8’s meditation on the first Adam as a model.

¹ This paper depends in large part on chapters 4 and 5 of my book, *The Jewish Targums and John’s Logos Theology* (Grand Rapids: Hendrickson/Baker, 2010), hereafter *JTJLT*. The 4th chapter is titled “The Son of Man Came Down From Heaven” (pp. 84-115), in which I discuss the theme of Jesus coming down from heaven (John 3:13; 6:38) as a theme that has continuity with the OT theme of God “coming down” (i.e. intervening in history) for various purposes (repeated in the ultimate descent, the incarnation), but also discontinuity in that in the incarnation he “came down” as a human being, so that these OT purposes for which God “came down” in OT times can find their eternal fulfillment. In chapter 5, “Jesus of Nazareth, Man of War,” I discuss the implications of the various “high and lifted up” passages in Isaiah to the words of Jesus in John. This paper has been revised as a result of feedback at the conference, including my reading of the other papers presented.

² See chapter 11 of *JTJLT*. The rest of the book is an extensive argument for an Aramaic (targumic) background to the Logos title, which concludes that calling Jesus “the Word” is tantamount to calling him “Yahweh the God of Israel.” An organizing theme of the Gospel is therefore “the Word became flesh and dwelt among us, and we beheld his glory” (John 1:14), as John shows us what it means for the God of Israel to take on human nature.

³ As pointed out in another paper from this conference; see Marida Nicolaci, “Divine Kingship and Jesus’ Identity in Jewish Messianism,” p. 7, n. 31.

We'll begin with a discussion of the OT background to the "Son of Man" title used of himself by Jesus; I support the following: (1) the title is based on "the son of man" in Ps 8:4, which looks back at the high position in which Adam was created; (2) it is also based on "one like a son of man" in Dan 7:13, who is an eschatologized version of the son of man referenced in Ps 8:4; (3) it is equivalent to Paul's designation of Jesus as "the last Adam" (1 Cor 15:45), and "the [Adam] who was to come" (Rom 5:14). The Aramaic translations of the OT prepared for recitation in the synagogue (Targums), in departures from literal translation, employ terminology that is consistent with the equation of "the Son of Man" from the Gospels with "the last Adam" in Paul. (4) The claim implied by use of the title was equivalent to that of "the Messiah" but it was enigmatic to his hearers, and thus served to veil Jesus' messianic claim. After his suffering, resurrection, and ascension, there was no longer any motive to veil this claim, which is the simple explanation of why in the NT letters the title is not used of Jesus, except as implied in the exposition of Psalm 8 by the author of Hebrews, which is also consistent with understanding Paul's teaching about Jesus as "the last Adam."

I also find that all of the uses of this title in John's Gospel can be placed into the categories suggested by the adaptation of Psalm 8:4-6 from Adam to Jesus found in Heb 2:6-10, namely, (1) the temporary descent of the Son of Man to a position "for a little while lower than the angels" (the incarnation and earthly ministry); (2) the glorification of the Son of Man (especially in his suffering); (3) the one who "brings many sons to glory" through believing in him; (4) the one to whom all authority is given. Additionally, examination of the passages dealing with the glorification of the Son of Man in light of allusions to passages in Isaiah suggest that the glorification of Jesus in his suffering is divine glorification, and is part of a pervasive theme in John according to which the person and work of Jesus Christ in the flesh is both a continuation of his pre-incarnate person and work, while at the same time involving a change in that work due to the incarnation, when he takes on a fully human nature, with its accompanying eternal consequences.

The Targums and the "Last Adam" in Paul.

"The first man, Adam" (1 Cor 15:45) comes across as a conflation of two translation possibilities for the Aramaic expression *'dm qdmy'* used to describe Adam in various Targum passages (*Tg. Neof.* Gen 2:8; 3:22; 48:22; Deut 4:32; *Tg. Ps.-J.* Gen 27:15; Exod 4:11; *Frg. Tg. P, V, and CTg. Z* Gen 48:22; *Tg. Ps.* 49:2; 69:31; 92:1; 94:10; *1st Tg. Esth.* 3:7; *2nd Tg. Esth.* 1:2).⁴ Some Targum translators render this expression "the first man" in English. But since *'dm* is not an Aramaic common noun, as it is in Hebrew, where it may also be a proper noun, other translators render the expression "the first Adam." Paul may be viewed as combining both

⁴ Also listed in *JTJLT*, 108, n. 36. See also Samson H. Levey, *The Targum of Ezekiel*, The Aramaic Bible 13 (Collegeville, Minn: Liturgical Press, 1987), 6-9, for that Targum's rendering of "son of man" (Heb. *bn 'dm*) by "son of Adam" (*br 'dm*) rather than the generic *br nš'*.

translation possibilities in 1 Cor 15:45; “the first man, Adam.”⁵ *Tg. Neofiti* also uses the expression “the son of man” (*br nš*), since the expression is used generically of human beings (thus equivalent to “the man”), when referring specifically to Adam. It does so in the following passages:

The Word of the Lord created the son of man; Gen 1:27

It is not proper that the son of man should be alone; Gen 2:18

We also have non-emphatic (indefinite) “son of man” (*br nš*) in *Tg. Neof.* and *Frg. Tg. P* Gen 1:26, “let us create man.”

Two other passages in *Tg. Neofiti* could be viewed either as referring to Adam individually or mankind generically:

There was regret before the Lord that he had created Adam (*mg.* the son of man); Gen 6:6

I will never again curse the earth on account of the son of man; Gen 8:21

So, Paul calls Adam “the first man, Adam,” in quoting Gen 2:7, while in the same chapter of Genesis *Tg. Neofiti* calls Adam both “the first man/Adam” (v. 8) and “the son of man” (v. 18). Whenever dealing with the Targums, of course, we have to keep in mind that all of the extant Targums post-date the first century, so we don’t know if any first century Targum in Palestine referred to Adam as “the son of man.”

OT Development of the Last Adam Theme.

While the expression “the first man/Adam” by itself does not imply that another “Adam” was expected, perhaps Paul picked up on the targumic/rabbinic expression to give Jesus the designation “last Adam,” or “[Adam] who was to come.” What is evident at least in hindsight, is that the OT itself has a recurring theme of a “new Adam,” who might be expected to make up for the failures of the first Adam, but who in practice always falls short and disappoints; such disappointments thus creating an expectation from the beginning for one who will not disappoint; thus, an eschatological Adam.

Adam and Eve at their creation were given a mandate to be fruitful, multiply, fill the earth and exercise dominion over it with its animals. Being uncorrupted images of God, their offspring would have been naturally righteous sons and daughters of God, exercising righteous dominion in all their works. The change due to sin entering the world introduces mortality and futility in man’s labor, and enmity among their two kinds of offspring. Cain is presented in Genesis 4 as like the serpent of Genesis 3 (a liar, murderer, cursed), so the suggestion is that humanity is by

⁵ In a note on *Tg. Neof.* Gen 2:18, Martin McNamara says that “the first Adam” in the Aramaic “corresponds to the Hebrew *’adam ha-rishon*, a common rabbinic designation for Adam; cf. also 1 Cor 15:45” (*Targum Neofiti 1: Genesis*, The Aramaic Bible 1A [Collegeville, Minn.: Liturgical Press, 1992], 57, n. 16). An interesting feature of *Tg. Neofiti* is that in several passages it retains the Hebrew definite article - *h’dm* (Gen 2:16; 3:12, 20 [mg.]; 4:1).

nature, apart from new creation, “offspring of the serpent,” having exchanged God-likeness for serpent-likeness, and the creation mandate of Gen 1:27 is altered in Gen 3:15 to envision a perpetual conflict between the righteous and the wicked, beginning with Cain and Abel, with victory over the serpent’s seed promised to the woman’s seed.⁶

Noah.

After the flood the commission that God gave to Noah and his sons is obviously reminiscent of the commission given to Adam and Eve (compare Gen 1:26-28 to 9:1-7). Besides the twin ideas of fruitfulness and dominion, Noah’s commission also recalls the creation of man as the divine image, as justification for capital punishment for murder. But the aftermath of this new beginning looks pretty much like that with the first Adam as a consequence of his fall; (1) the new Adam himself is still a sinner, (2) and the race of which he is progenitor shows the same division between righteous and wicked – the two seeds of Gen 3:15, and the tendency over time goes to universal wickedness (Gen 9:20-27; 11:1-9). What is needed is a new Adam who is the righteous progenitor of a righteous race, but as history unfolds it becomes clear that this is not the reality with Noah.

Abraham.

Abraham is given an Adam-like commission in Gen 17:2-6, 16, where the ideas of fruitfulness and dominion appear not as commands, but as promises, and the theme of dominion undergoes a change from dominion over the earth and the animal kingdom to dominion over other peoples (v. 6, “kings shall come forth from you;” and v. 16, “kings of peoples shall be from [Sarah]”). Perhaps because of these allusions to the creation mandate in Genesis 17, Paul in Rom 4:13 says that Abraham received the promise that he would be “heir of the world (κόσμος), not “heir of the promised land.” But as in the case of Noah, Abraham does not live up to the expectation of a new Adam. Abraham’s sins are recorded in a way that reminds the attentive reader of the first Adam’s sin, in theme and wording, while among his offspring we see the same two seeds at enmity (Ishmael and Isaac, Genesis 21) as was the case with Noah and Adam.⁷

⁶ This theme is developed in the author’s “The Curse on the Serpent: Genesis 3:15 in Biblical Theology and Hermeneutics,” PhD diss., Westminster Theological Seminary, Glenside, PA, 1997; http://postbiblical.info/PDFS/The_Curse_on_the_Serpent.pdf. See pp. iii, 179-210; 310-16.

⁷ The incident of Sarai giving Hagar to Abram utilizes wording from the fall narrative: “Abram listened to the voice of Sarai” (Gen 16:2; cf. Gen 3:17, “because you have listened to the voice of your wife”), and “Sarai took . . . and gave her to her husband Abram” (Gen 16:3; cf. Gen 3:6, “she took . . . and she gave also to her husband”). We also see the theme of dissatisfaction with God’s provision in both narratives, the idea that God is withholding something good that you should have, so you must go outside his will to get it. The incidents of Abram/Abraham lying about his wife as his sister can be analyzed similarly. See Werner Berg, “Der Sündenfall Abrahams und Saras nach Gen 16, 1-6” (*Biblische Notizen* 19 [1982]: 7-14), and “Nochmals: Ein Sündenfall Abrahams – der erste – in Gen 12, 10-20” (*Biblische Notizen* 21 [1983]: 7-15). I also discussed this in Ronning, “The Curse on the Serpent,” 193-95, and in my article, “The Naming of Isaac: the Role of the Wife/Sister Episodes in the Redaction of Genesis” (*WTJ* 53 [1991], 1-27). Also available at:

https://www.academia.edu/7387269/The_Naming_of_Isaac_The_Role_of_the_Wife_Sister_Episodes_in_the_Redac

Isaac.

We do not have any record of God addressing Isaac in terms of the adamic mandate/promise given to Abraham in Genesis 17. However, Exod 6:3 does say that God “appeared to Abraham, Isaac and Jacob as El Shaddai.” It is as El Shaddai that God appeared to Abraham in Genesis 17, treating him as a new Adam; likewise to Jacob in Genesis 35 (noted below), so perhaps Exod 6:3 indicates there was such a revelation to Isaac as well. While that is speculative, what is not in doubt is that whatever expectation there would be of some kind of specialness in Isaac due to the miraculous circumstances of his conception and birth, he disappoints and falls short, just like his father. In fact his sin of lying about Rebekah in Genesis 26 repeats the sin of Abraham in Genesis 12 and 20. The brotherly enmity of previous generations exists also in the twins born to him, Jacob and Esau (Genesis 27).

Jacob.

Much the same terminology used in Genesis 17 is used also with Jacob in Gen 35:11-12, in a similar context as Genesis 17 (use of the name El Shaddai, and a patriarchal name change). But again we see as history unfolds, Jacob fails to live up to any expectation of being a new Adam: (1) he is himself a sinner, and (2) he has the same two seeds at enmity among his offspring (Joseph and his brothers), which is the main theme running through the rest of Genesis.

David.

One can find the same two themes of fruitfulness and dominion in the promises to David in Nathan’s oracle, 2 Sam 7:11–16 (also 1 Chron 17:10–14). In this case the phraseology is further altered from the original creation mandate, as the idea of fruitfulness is given as a promise of God building a “house” for David. David’s reaction to these promises could be understood as a recognition that this theme of the new Adam from Genesis was being applied to him: “And this is the law of mankind” (*wəzōʾt tōrat hāʾādām*; 2 Sam 7:19).⁸ But we see the same disqualifiers in the life of David as in the patriarchs who seemed to have been brought forward as a “new Adam.” His great sin with Bathsheba appears as an aggravated version of Abraham’s sin in Genesis 20, where Abraham feared for his life because of his beautiful wife; David is the kind of king Abraham feared in Genesis 20, in that he killed a man to get his beautiful wife. We also see the two seeds of Genesis 3:15 among David’s sons. Solomon was loved by the LORD but Amnon

tion_of_Genesis.

⁸ For difficulties with this passage and its parallel in 1 Chron 17:17, see Ronning, “The Curse on the Serpent,” 310-12. Some might object to seeing David’s phraseology in 2 Sam 7:19 as alluding to language from Genesis 1, as anachronistic. But one should take note of the language of Moses in Deut 4:32, where he casually refers to the fact that the exodus miracles had never before happened, “since the day God created Adam on the earth” (*lāmin hayyôm ʾāšer bārā ʾēlōhīm ʾādām ʾal hāʾāreš*). Also note that *wəzōʾt tōrat* or *wəzōʾt hattōrah* is used commonly throughout the law of Moses, especially the so-called “P” sections (Lev 6:2, 9, 14, 25; 7:1, 11, 37; 11:46; 12:7; 13:59; 14:32, 54, 57; 15:32; Num 6:13; 21; 19:14; Deut 4:44.). Perhaps the closest conceptually to the understanding of Gen 1:28 suggested above for 2 Sam 7:19 is Num 6:13, 21, [*wəzōʾt tōrat hannāzîr*, “[and] this is the law of [i.e., regulations governing the conduct of] the Nazirite.”

is shown to be worse than Canaanite Shechem (comparing Genesis 34 to 2 Samuel 11); Absalom murdered his brother and tries to do so to his father; Adonijah “exalted himself” to become a usurper, evidently intending to put the life of Solomon and his mother in jeopardy (1 Kgs 1:5, 10, 21).

Psalm 8.

“What is man, that you are mindful of him, the son of man, that you pay attention to him” (Ps 8:4) has a certain similarity to David’s response to Nathan’s oracle; “Who am I . . . and what is my house, that you have brought me thus far?” (2 Sam 7:18). The Psalm continues with a meditation on the creation mandate given to Adam and Eve in Gen 1:27-28. He speaks of man being “crowned with glory and majesty” (*kābôd wəhādār*), and perhaps David could see a parallel with his own experience. Again, from David’s response to Nathan’s oracle; “And what more can David [say] to you, for honoring (*kābôd*) your servant” (1 Chron 17:18). Another Psalm of David uses the same words for “glory and majesty” from Ps 8:5 for the honor given by God to David: “You set a crown of fine gold upon his head . . . Great is his glory (*kabôdô*) through your salvation; splendor and majesty (*hōd wəhādār*) you place upon him” (Ps 21:3, 5). Since the OT sets up an expectation of a new Adam, and since in the OT the Messiah is prophetically called “David” (Jer 30:9; Ezek 34:23-24; 37:24-25; Hos 3:5), it would be fitting for Jesus to appropriate language from David’s meditation on the adamic mandate, which was also used for David himself, when Jesus began his ministry. Calling himself “the Son of Man” can thus be seen as a veiled claim to be the expected “Messiah.”

It is often overlooked that in the first appearance of the “Son of Man” title in the canonical order of the NT (Matt 8:20, = Luke 9:58), as well as the chronologically earliest recorded use of the title in the ministry of Jesus (John 1:51), an allusion to Ps 8:4 can be seen. Also of interest, since Jacob was one of the OT new Adam prototypes, is that both of these passages have reminiscences of Jacob at Bethel. Matthew 8:20, “the Son of man has nowhere to lay his head,” in contrast to foxes (a beast of the field) and birds of the sky is (1) ironic in that the first Adam was given lordship over these creatures who now seem better off than he (Ps 8:6-8), (2) less obviously, it reminds us of Jacob at Bethel, who took one of the stones of the place for a pillow, since otherwise he had nowhere to lay his head (Gen 28:11).

In the case of John 1:51, the allusion to Jacob at Bethel is the obvious one, since Jesus is saying that Nathanael (and others, since “you” is plural) will see something like what Jacob saw at Bethel (angels ascending and descending; Gen 28:12). At the same time, the idea of angels ascending and descending upon the Son of Man gives us a picture of the Son of Man as “lower than the angels,” thus pointing to Ps 8:5.

Daniel 7:13.

Dependence on Dan 7:13 of Jesus' use of "the Son of Man" in reference to himself is of course obvious and well known, since Jesus makes unmistakable references to Dan 7:13 while calling himself the Son of Man (Matt 24:30 26:64; Mark 13:26; 14:62; Luke 21:27). Daniel sees in his dream "one like a son of man" coming in the clouds of heaven, who receives from God "dominion, glory, and an eternal kingdom," so that "all peoples, nations, and men of every language might serve him" (Dan 7:13-14). This "son of man" (Aramaic *br 'nš*, "human being") contrasts with the previously described four kingdoms, which are described with various features of, to use the language of Psalm 8, beasts of the field and birds of the sky (Dan 7:3-8). Of special interest is the first beast, "like a lion" with "wings of an eagle," who has its wings plucked and is "made to stand up on two feet like a man (Aram. 'nš); a heart of a man (Aram. 'nš) was also given to it" (v. 4). This transformation is commonly related to the experience of king Nebuchadnezzar, who, because of his pride, was deprived of his sanity for a time, given a beast's mind, dwelling with "the beasts of the field," and "eating grass like cattle," with hair and nails like birds' feathers and claws, until he lifted his eyes to heaven and his human reason returned to him (Dan 4:16, 25-26, 32-37). Also of interest is that Nebuchadnezzar before his judgment is described in terms similar to those contemplated by David in Ps 8:7-8; he is like a tree which gives refuge to beasts of the field and birds of the sky (vv. 12, 14, 21).

It would therefore be quite natural to interpret the "one like a son of man" in Daniel 7 as an eschatological version of the adamic "son of man" described in Psalm 8; a "last Adam."⁹ Combined with the observation that various OT figures seem to be put forth as a "new Adam," but who turn out not to be up to the task, one could also view the one like a son of man of Dan 7:13 in contrast with these OT men who fell short. In this respect it seems quite fitting that both Matt 8:20 (= Luke 9:58) and John 1:51 allude to Jacob at Bethel. Indeed, at Bethel Jacob was on a two-fold mission which can be compared and contrasted with the mission of Jesus. Jacob left his father's house to go to a foreign land in order to (1) save his life, which was in danger due to his deceit; (2) to get a wife, after which he contemplated returning to his father's house in peace (Genesis 27-28). Jesus likewise left his Father's house on a mission, and would return when the mission was accomplished. He went to seek a bride, the church, which makes it fitting for John to include the scene of Jesus meeting the Samaritan woman at a well (John 4), which has many points of contact with the several OT scenes where a man meets a woman at a well (Genesis 24, 29; Exodus 2), as well as when God "met" Israel at a well and miraculously provided water for his people (Exod 17:1-6). Genesis 29 describes Jacob meeting his future wife Rachel at a well. The *Palestinian Targums* (at Gen 28:10) claim that when Jacob lifted the stone from the mouth of the well, the water sprang up and the well overflowed for twenty years, the time that he dwelt in Haran. This legend adds to our understanding of Jesus' answer to the Samaritan woman's question, "You are not greater than our father Jacob, are you?" (John 4:12). Jesus answers in terms that indeed show how much greater he is than Jacob according to this legend: "Whoever

⁹ So George W. E. Nickelsburg, "Son of Man," *ABD* 6:143.

drinks from the water that I shall give him shall never thirst, but the water that I shall give him shall become in him a well of water *springing up to eternal life*" (v. 14).¹⁰ Jesus is as much greater than Jacob as eternity is greater than 20 years!

As for Jacob's other mission in Genesis 28, he was fleeing from his father's house in order to save his own life. His life was in danger due to his own deceit in the matter of the blessing which he tried to trick from his brother (Genesis 27). In contrast, Jesus left his Father's house in order to lay down his life, in order to save Jacob's (eternal) life (and ours), redeeming us from such sins. So the two missions of Jacob when applied to Jesus become one - he left his Father's house to gain his bride (the church) by giving his life to save hers. In this Jesus showed why he is the worthy "new Adam," in contrast to even the best men of the OT. Abraham twice lied about beautiful Sarah, subjecting her to potential defilement in order to save his own life. Isaac did the same concerning Rebekah, explaining, "I thought I might die on account of her" (Gen 26:9). Jesus in contrast came to "die on account of her." He "loved the church and gave himself up for her, to make her holy" (Eph 5:25-26). The Samaritan woman obviously then, symbolizes the church. In contrast to Rebekah, clearly presented in Genesis 24, when she meets Abraham's servant at the well, as one who passes the test of good character, and is beautiful besides, the very model of a desirable bride, the Samaritan woman is the very model of an undesirable bride, so that Christians can see how we appear in the sight of God before we experience the grace of God and are progressively transformed into that model bride, as Paul explained to the Corinthians: "I betrothed you to one husband, that to Christ I might present you as a pure virgin" (2 Cor 11:2).

Psalm 8 and Psalm 110.

Psalm 110:1, "The LORD says to my Lord, 'Sit at my right hand, until I make your enemies a footstool for your feet,'" is another passage that can be viewed as reflecting an eschatological version of a theme from Psalm 8. As we noted, Dan 7:13 has the idea of future dominion over kingdoms represented as animals, which can be related to the original human dominion over animals mentioned in Ps 8:6-8. Psalm 110:1, with the idea of enemies being put under foot can be related to Ps 8:6, "You put all things under his feet." And just as what David says about Adam in Psalm 8 has parallels with what God did for David, the same can be observed about Ps 110:1. Solomon sent this message to Hiram king of Tyre; "David my father was unable to build a house for the name of the LORD his God because of the wars which surrounded him, until the LORD put them under the soles of his feet" (1 Kgs 5:3). At his trial, Jesus brought Dan 7:13 and Ps 110:1 together: "You shall see the Son of Man sitting at the right hand of Power, and coming on the clouds of heaven" (Matt 26:64; Mark 14:62). Paul, on the other hand, twice connected Ps 110:1 with Ps 8:6. "He must reign until he has put all his enemies

¹⁰ For exposition of John 4 in light of these OT accounts, see chapter 6 of *JTJLT*, "Jesus the Bridegroom of His People" (pp. 143-55).

under his feet . . . For he has put all things in subjection under his feet” (1 Cor 15:25, 27). “He raised him from the dead, and seated him at his right hand . . . and he put all things in subjection under his feet” (Eph 1:20, 22). Likewise the exposition of Psalm 8 in Hebrews 2 is preceded by a quote of Ps 110:1 (Heb 1:13).

Hebrews 2:6–10 and the Son of Man in John.

Once the allusions in Matt 8:20/Luke 9:58, and John 1:51 to “the son of man” in Psalm 8 are recognized, we can readily see why Heb 2:6-10 expounds the Psalm in the light of the coming of the Last Adam. Because Psalm 8 looks back into history, to the first Adam, some adaptation is required to apply the Psalm to the eschatological Adam. In this adaptation, we see an example of the apostolic hermeneutical principle, “same words, different meaning.”

In Ps 8:5, both parts of the verse refer to the same thing: the high position in which our first parents were created; “a little *bit* lower than the angels,” and “crowned with glory and majesty.” Such exaltation is made evident in man’s being placed over the animal creation. In the case of Jesus, the two parts of this verse refer to quite different events. “A little bit lower than the angels” in the case of Jesus is not an exaltation from the dust but rather a temporary humbling: “Made for a little while lower than the angels” (Heb 2:9), i.e. the incarnation and earthly ministry of Jesus, when he left “the glory that I had with you before the world existed” (John 17:5). Adam was glorified dust, a ruler; Jesus was deity humbled to be a servant (Phil 2:6-8).

The second part of Ps 8:5, “crowned with glory and majesty,” is applied to Jesus’ suffering: “We do see . . . Jesus, because of the suffering of death crowned with glory and honor, so that by the grace of God he might taste death for every man” (Heb 2:9). A number of versions essentially rewrite this verse so that the order is suffering first, followed by glorification, which is clearly opposed by the Greek word ὅπως, “in order that,” which makes the glorification of Jesus (counter-intuitively) precede his death. As we shall see, this theme is quite evident in John.

The author of Hebrews goes on to describe the purpose of Jesus’ sufferings as “bringing many sons to glory” (2:10). Adam’s fall brought many sons to shame and dishonor, Jesus tasted death to bring the fallen to glory.

Twelve times in John, Jesus calls himself “the Son of Man.” Here is how they fit into the categories of interpretation suggested by the interpretation of Heb 2:6-10:

(1) John 3:13 refers to the Son of Man descending from heaven, John 1:50 depicts him lower than the angels, John 6:62 refers to the Son of Man ascending to where he was before. Together, these three uses of the title fit the adaptation of Ps 8:5a in Hebrews 2, “For a little while [his whole life as a man on earth], lower than the angels.”

(2) In John 3:14; 8:28; 12:23, 34; 13:31 Jesus speaks of the Son of Man being “lifted up” or “glorified” which refer to the suffering of Jesus, agreeing with what we noted above concerning Heb 2:9. Jesus also speaks of being lifted up in John 12:32 without using the Son of Man title. Another use of “Son of Man” in this chapter is the crowd’s question, “Who is this ‘Son of Man’?” (v. 34). No clear answer to this question appears in the context, but a few days later an answer comes when the Son of Man is being brought forth by Pilate, “crowned with (mock) glory and majesty” in his suffering, and Pilate unwittingly quotes Zech 6:12 (where the high priest Joshua is symbolically given a crown) and completes the man/son of man parallelism from Ps 8:4 with John 12:34, as “Who is this ‘Son of Man’?” is answered a few days later by Pilate, “Behold the man!” (John 19:5).¹¹

(3) The first Adam was the progenitor of the human race, but through his fall we were brought to shame and disgrace; the role of the last Adam in Heb 2:10 is to “bring many sons to glory.” This state of glory is accomplished through faith in Jesus, and three more Son of Man sayings in John relate to this role. In John 6:27 and 53 Jesus is the bread of life, bringing eternal life to those who partake by performing “the work of God,” which is to believe in Jesus (John 6:29). In John 9:35, Jesus asks the man born blind, “Do you believe in the Son of Man?”

(4) One last Son of Man saying relates to the idea of dominion. “Just as the Father has life in himself, so he gave to the Son to have life in himself. And he gave him authority to execute judgment, because he is the Son of Man” (John 5:26-27). Since the authority spoken of here is over men, one could also more readily relate this verse the eschatological Adam, “one like a son of man,” of Dan 7:13.¹²

The Glorification of the Son of Man in John and Isaiah.

Expanding on point (2) above, comparison of the four sayings of Jesus in John about being lifted up with four corresponding passages in Isaiah shows the extent of the glorification of Jesus to be divine glorification. In fact, Isaiah by itself hints in this direction. First of all, it is commonly recognized that when Jesus says to Nicodemus, “As Moses lifted up the serpent in the wilderness, so must the Son of Man be lifted up,” the OT reference is not just to the bronze serpent incident in Numbers 21, but to Isa 52:13, where the term “lifted up” is used. “Behold, my Servant will act wisely. He will be high, and he will be lifted up, and he will be greatly exalted.” “Lifted up” is the *niphal* of the root *n-š-ʿ*, and is translated in LXX with the same Greek word as

¹¹ Zechariah 6:12 says, “Behold, a man whose name is Branch, for he will branch out from where he is and build the temple of the LORD.” *Tg. Zech.* says, “Behold the man whose name is Messiah. And he will be anointed.”

¹² Crispin Fletcher-Louis pursued this theme in another conference paper, “Jesus is ‘Equal with God’ Because the Son of God is the Son of Man (John 5).” Fletcher-Louis notes that besides sharing the “son of man” terminology with John 5:27, LXX Dan 7:14 has *καὶ ἐδόθη αὐτῷ ἐξουσία*, compared to John 5:27, *καὶ ἐξουσίαν ἔδωκεν αὐτῷ*. LXX Dan 7:14 also translates “His dominion is an everlasting dominion” with *καὶ ἡ ἐξουσία αὐτοῦ ἐξουσία αἰώνιος*. He also notes that Dan 12:2 speaks of the next subject in Jesus’ discourse (vv. 28-29), resurrection to both condemnation and vindication, and that the heavenly scene which is the context of Dan 7:13-14 could be taken along the lines of John 5:23, that men should honor the Son just as they honor the Father.

used in the passages in John that we have been discussing (ὕψόω). The three verbs in Hebrew are actually only represented by two in the LXX; the other is δοξάζω, again the same word used for “glorified” in the passages in John that we have been discussing, so in LXX the Servant is to be “lifted up and glorified.” “He will be high” in Isa 52:13 is from the Hebrew root *rûm* (*qal*).

“High and lifted up” in Isaiah 2:12-14.

The two verbs “high and lifted up” used together have quite an interesting usage throughout Isaiah. First of all, they are used quite negatively, and repeatedly, in Isa 2:12-14, to describe proud, sinful, idolatrous men.

¹¹The haughty look of man will be humbled, and the highness (noun *rûm*) of man will be brought low, and the LORD alone will be exalted in that day.

¹²For the LORD of Hosts will have a day of reckoning, against everyone who is proud and high, and against everyone who is lifted up, that he may be humbled. ¹³And it will be against the cedars of Lebanon that are high and lifted up. . . . ¹⁴Against all the high mountains, against all the hills that are lifted up. . . .

¹⁷And the haughtiness of man will be humbled, and the highness (noun *rûm*) of man will be brought low, and the LORD alone will be exalted in that day. ¹⁸But the idols will completely vanish.

The expectation, then, of mere men being “high and lifted up” is that they will be brought low in divine judgment of their pride and idolatry. One thinks by way of historical example the already mentioned son of David and would-be king Adonijah, who against the expressed will of God “exalted himself” (1 Kgs 1:5; the verb is the *hithpael* of the root *n-š-ʔ*, used in these “lifted up” passages in Isaiah). One could also mention another unworthy son of David, king Uzziah, who was blessed by God early in his reign but due to his success became proud and corrupt, entering the temple to burn incense, a role reserved for the sons of Aaron, and was struck with leprosy on the forehead, the place where the legitimate high priest had a turban with a plate inscribed “Holy to the LORD” (2 Chronicles 26; Exod 28:36-37). The verb used to describe Uzziah negatively as “proud” (*lit.*, his heart was high; *qal* of *g-b-h*) is also the verb used of the Servant following “high” and “lifted up” in Isa 52:13, obviously in a very positive sense: “he will be greatly exalted” (*wəgābah mə’ōd*). The case of Uzziah’s judgment is an appropriate introduction to the next place in Isaiah where we find this “high and lifted up” language, “in the year of king Uzziah’s death.”

“High and lifted up” in Isaiah 6.

Consistent with the twofold declaration that “the LORD alone will be exalted in that day,” framing this passage about the humbling of men who are “high and lifted up” in pride, Isaiah 6

uses these “high and lifted up” words to describe the LORD in his vision to Isaiah, in which he sees himself undone. In light of this passage from Isaiah 2, it is as though Isaiah experiences his own personal “day of the LORD,” although the outcome in his case is positive, as he is not just humbled but cleansed and fit for divine service.

¹In the year of the death of king Uzziah, I saw the Lord (ʿădōnāy), seated on his throne, high and lifted up, and the train of his robe filled the temple . . . ⁵“Woe is me, for I am undone . . . for my eyes have seen the King, the LORD of Hosts.”

This passage can be related to John 8:28, where Jesus says, “When you lift up the Son of Man, then you will know that I am he,” because, (1) it is spoken in the temple, where (in the first temple) Isaiah saw the one “high and lifted up;” (2) even though Jesus refers to himself as a man, he is speaking according to the divine speech found in Deut 32:39 (including its Aramaic paraphrases) and multiple times in Isaiah, especially close to Isa 43:10 which has in common a context of predicting the future while proclaiming “you will know that I am he.”¹³

Another “lifted up” passage in John that can be related to Isaiah’s vision is John 12:39-41. John, likely responding to an implied objection to the messiahship of Jesus along the lines of “If he was the Messiah would he not have been received as such by the Jews?”, quotes Isa 6:10 to explain why they “could not believe” (v. 39), after which John says, “These things Isaiah said, because he saw his glory, and spoke of him” (v. 41), implying that it was the pre-incarnate Christ seen by Isaiah in the temple; which also agrees with John 1:18, “No man has seen God (i.e. the Father) at any time.” Isaiah 6:1 is also partly quoted in *Tg. Ps.-J. Deut 4:7*, potentially relevant to why John chose to call Jesus “the Word;” as the *Targum* has Moses use the wording of Isa 6:1 in targumic paraphrase which differs from the extant *Isaiah Targum*, part of *Targum Jonathan of the Prophets*; “For the Word of the Lord sits upon his throne, high and lifted up, and hears our prayers.” So, if “no man has seen God [the Father] at any time” (John 1:18), when Isaiah’s eyes

¹³ I discuss the 22 “I am he” sayings in John in chapter 9 of *JTJLT*. John 8:24 (“unless you believe that I am he”) together with 8:28 form a more complete parallel to Isa 43:10, “In order that you might know and believe me, and understand that I am he.” John 13:19 is also a close parallel to Isa 43:10, again with the similar context of predictive prophecy; “I am telling you before it comes to pass, so that when it does occur, you might know that I am he.” No mere human prophet spoke in such terms. The other “I am he” sayings in Isaiah are in 41:4; 43:13, 25; 46:4; 48:12; 51:12; 52:6. Isaiah 52:6 (“Therefore my people shall know my name; therefore, in that day, I am he, the one who is speaking, ‘Here I am’”) has close, but often overlooked wording to John 4:26 (“I am he, the one who is speaking to you”). *Tg. Ps.-J. Deut 32:39* reads in part, “When the Word of the Lord shall be revealed to redeem his people, he will say to all the nations, ‘See now that I am he who is and was, and I am he who will be in the future, and there is no other God besides me. I, by my Word put to death and bring back to life’” (cf. Rev 1:4, 8; 4:8). The “I am he” with reference to past, present, and future can be seen in the threefold “I am he” at the Feast of Booths, present in 8:24 (“Unless you believe that I am he, you will die in your sins”); future in 8:28 (“When you lift up the Son of Man you will know that I am he”); past in 8:58 (“Before Abraham was born, I am he”). Note also Heb 13:8; “Jesus Christ, the same, yesterday and today, and forever.” *Tg. Neof. Deut 32:39* reads in part “See now that I, I in my Word am he, and there is no other God besides me. I am he who causes the living to die in this world, and who brings to life the dead in the world to come. I am he who strikes, and I am he who heals” (similarly *Frg. Tg. V Deut 32:39*).

“saw the LORD of Hosts,” he must have seen the Son of God in his pre-incarnate glory (cf. John 17:5).

I mentioned above that LXX uses “lifted up and glorified” in Isa 52:13, even though the Hebrew does not use the word “glorified.” The same is not the case in LXX Isa 6:1, but the Greek does bring in the concept of glory another way. Where the Hebrew says “the train of his robe filled the temple,” LXX says “the house was filled with his glory.”¹⁴ Similarly, the *Isaiah Targum* says “the temple was filled with the splendor of his glory.” In *Tg. Isa.* 6:1 Isaiah says that he saw “the glory of the Lord” resting on a throne, and in v. 5 he says “my eyes have seen the glory of the Shekinah of the eternal king, the Lord of Hosts,” and in v. 8 he says, “I heard the voice of the Word of the Lord,” etc.¹⁵

“High and lifted up” in Isaiah 33:10.

A second time this “high and lifted up” language is used of God is in connection with a divine promise to deliver Judah from Sennacherib. After about 30 years of promising such deliverance through Isaiah, during which time the Assyrians have conquered and exiled the northern kingdom, defeated all of Judah’s allies, and almost completely conquered Judah, with Jerusalem the only remaining fortified city, the LORD announces that the time for fulfillment has come:¹⁶

Now I will arise, says the LORD, now I will go on high (*hithpolel* of *rûm*; LXX uses the verb $\delta\omicron\xi\acute{\alpha}\zeta\omega$, “glorified”), now I will be lifted up (*niphal impf.* of $\eta\text{-}\acute{\sigma}\text{-}\acute{\nu}$).

So as in Isa 52:13, “high” and “lifted up” in Hebrew goes into Greek as “lifted up” and “glorified,” the key words used of the glorification of the Son of Man in John. Perhaps because in one of the passages promising deliverance from the Assyrians the verb “pass over” (*qal* of $\rho\text{-}\acute{\sigma}\text{-}\eta$) is used (Isa 31:5), there was a belief that the deliverance from Sennacherib happened at Passover, evidenced in *Tg. 2 Chron.* 32:21-22; “The Word of the Lord sent the angel Gabriel, and during the night of the Passover . . . he destroyed every mighty warrior and officer and commander in the camp of the king of Assyria.” Seven centuries later, when this divine Word became flesh, a few days before Passover he says he is going to do it again:

¹⁴ This reading in the Greek was pointed out in another conference paper, “Johannine Christology and Prophetic Traditions: The Case of Isaiah,” by Catrin H. Williams, who discussed a number of cases where the Greek departs from the Hebrew in ways that would be of interest to John’s presentation of Jesus.

¹⁵ See my article, “The *Targum of Isaiah* and the Johannine Literature,” *WTJ* 69 (2007): 247-78 (also available at https://www.academia.edu/7847884/The_Targum_of_Isaiah_and_the_Johannine_Literature) for evidence of John’s acquaintance with and use of something like the extant *Isaiah Targum*.

¹⁶ See “Jesus of Nazareth, Man of War,” chapter 5 of *JTJLT* for fuller exposition of this passage and its connection to John’s Gospel, esp. pp. 121-27.

Now judgment is upon this world; now the ruler of this world will be cast out.
And I, if I be lifted up from the earth, will draw all men to myself. (John 12:31-32)

To complete the parallel, another such promise is spoken a few days later in the upper room:
Now is the Son of Man glorified, and God is glorified in him. (John 13:31)

Together the two passages give us the threefold “now” and the combination “lifted up” and “glorified” of Isa 33:10. Isaiah 33:13 is also relevant here: “You who are far away [other nations surrounding Judah], hear what I have done; you who are near [Judeans], acknowledge my power.” Likewise the deliverance Jesus is about to accomplish will be for those both near and far: “I . . . will draw all men to myself” (note the mention of “Greeks” in the context as prodding the promise of Jesus; v. 20; also note John 7:35, where they ask if Jesus intends to go and teach the Greeks among the dispersion). With Isa 33:10, 13 (and its historical context) as background, we can see John 12:31-31; 13:13 as the prelude to divine warfare, just as in the time of Isaiah, so that the glorification of Jesus is to be understood as divine glorification in victorious warfare, of which the defeat of Sennacherib is just a figure for the defeat of “the ruler of this world.” The picture of Jerusalem as on the verge of annihilation in the time of Hezekiah, saved “in the nick of time,” when all human hope for deliverance was lost, as a picture of salvation through Jesus might well have inspired Paul’s words to the Romans, “While we were still helpless, at the right time, Christ died for the ungodly” (Rom 5:6).

“High and lifted up” in Isaiah 57:15.

For thus says the one who is high and lifted up, who lives forever, whose name is Holy; “I dwell on a high and holy place, yet also with the contrite and lowly of spirit.”

This “high and lifted up” passage is relevant to another saying in John 12; it is a saying quoted by the crowd back to Jesus, and its wording is quite like Jesus’ words to Nicodemus in the first “lifted up” saying (John 3:14), rather than a saying of Jesus quoted by John in John 12.

We have heard out of the law that the Christ is to remain forever, so how can you say, “the Son of Man must be lifted up”? Who is this “Son of Man”? (John 12:34).

Perhaps they were thinking of Isa 9:6, with its promise of one who would reign forever on the throne of David. If he is to reign forever, how can he be “lifted up”? One of the promised one’s names in that passage is “Mighty God” (*’ēl gibbôr*), used in the next chapter to describe the God of Israel (Isa 10:21, “A remnant will return . . . to the Mighty God). If the Messiah is divine, then there is no conflict between him “remaining forever,” and being “lifted up,” since that is

how the Holy and Mighty God describes himself in Isa 57:15: He is “lifted up,” and “lives forever;” the one who is to die by being “lifted up” will nevertheless “remain forever.”

To sum up, in Isaiah and other OT passages, mere men who are “high and lifted up” (including sons of David) are condemned and destined to be humbled, for the God of Israel alone will be exalted, the one who describes himself three times as high and lifted up. What does it say then about the nature of the servant whom he describes approvingly as one who will be high and lifted up in Isa 52:13? How could he be just a man? The description of “one like a son of man, coming with the clouds of heaven” in Dan 7:13 leaves the nature of this coming one somewhat open, and it would be possible, as some do, to interpret him merely as a representation of “the saints of the Most High” who receive the kingdom (Dan 7:18). While he receives “dominion and glory,” the same is true of other men, beginning with Adam (so Psalm 8). These passages in Isaiah show the extent of the glorification of the promised redeemer, as he is given a title and description reserved for the God of Israel himself. At the same time, the servant who is said to be high and lifted up is portrayed as a real man, even experiencing the ultimate human experience, death (Isa 53:8-9). And opposite to the “high and lifted up” (proud, idolatrous) men of chapter 2, the servant of Isaiah 53 is guiltless and full of God’s favor.

“High and lifted up” in Isaiah 52:13.

Such exaltation certainly appears paradoxical in the fourth servant song. Isaiah 53:2 says that he has “no majesty that we should look upon him,” using the word for majesty in Ps 8:5 and Ps 21:5 discussed above (*hādār*). Apparently the human perspective (no majesty) is different than the divine perspective (he will be high and lifted up, and greatly exalted). But of course there are other paradoxical features of the Song, and the prophet even acknowledges the difference between man’s perspective and intuition, and God’s purpose (esp. vv. 4-6). One of these paradoxes is that the Servant will be “cut off out of the land of the living” (v. 8), yet, “He will see his seed, he will prolong his days, and the good pleasure of the LORD will prosper in his hand” (v. 10). Here we can see a connection to the theme of the last Adam/Son of Man as the progenitor of a righteous seed, the one who through his (paradoxically) glorious suffering, “brings many sons to glory” (Heb 2:10).

Perhaps the deepest paradox of the fourth Servant Song appears when we contrast the “high and lifted up” (i.e. glorified) language not just with the Servant’s suffering, but when we look at the verbs used to describe what God is doing to him. “It pleased the LORD to crush him” (v. 10); “He was crushed for our iniquities” (v. 5). The verb in both cases is the *piel/pual* of *d-k-ʿ*, the verb used of God’s historical defeat of the serpent/dragon Rahab (Ps 89:10), and is reminiscent of the curse on the serpent, “He shall strike you on the head” (Gen 3:15). “He was pierced through (*polal* of *ḥ-l-l*) for our transgressions” (v. 5). Again, this verb is used of God’s defeat of the serpent dragon Rahab just two chapters earlier; “Awake . . . O arm of the LORD, . . . was it not you who cut Rahab in pieces? Who pierced (*polel* of *ḥ-l-l*) the dragon?” (Isa 51:9). I

have made the case that Rahab is an OT name for the cursed serpent of Gen 3:15.¹⁷ This interpretation would certainly be consistent with Paul's observation that Jesus "became a curse for us" (Gal 3:13). And we can then relate this use of "high and lifted up" to the remaining "lifted up" passage in John, its first; "As Moses lifted up the serpent in the wilderness, so must the Son of man be lifted up, that whoever believes may in him have eternal life" (John 3:14-15). One could say that Isaiah 53 does indeed portray the servant as one who is lifted up and has been dealt with, by God himself, like the cursed serpent. "To whom has the arm of the LORD been revealed?" (Isa 53:1). The "arm of the LORD" was petitioned in Isa 51:9 to awaken as instrument of God's judgment against the evil serpent/dragon Rahab as at the Red Sea crossing, but now from all appearances this arm of judgment is directed at his righteous Servant. That is what "we thought" (Isa 53:4); but in reality, this time also the ultimate target of the LORD's arm is the same, "the ruler of this world" (John 12:31).

At the beginning of his Gospel, John says that as a consequence of the divine Word becoming flesh and dwelling among them, "we saw his glory . . . full of grace and truth" (John 1:14). Most interpreters see "full of grace and truth" as John's translation of the Hebrew expression *rab ḥésed we'ēmet* used in God's self description to Moses on Mt. Sinai after the golden calf incident (Exod 34:6). Such an interpretation is certainly consistent with seeing an Aramaic background to the Logos title, as multiple Targum versions of this passage have this revelation to Moses, this divine self description, as a revelation of the divine Word.¹⁸ So in targumic language, it was the divine Word (pre-incarnate Son in John's adaptation) who described himself to Moses in such terms.

Recall also that this revelation came in response to the request of Moses, "Show me your glory" (Exod 33:18). The divine response was "I will make all my *goodness* pass before you, and will proclaim the name of the LORD before you" (v. 19). So John is saying that when the pre-incarnate Word became flesh, his disciples had an experience comparable to Moses, a revelation of the divine goodness/glory, beginning at the wedding at Cana, when "he manifested his glory" (John 2:11), but most of all as the purpose for which he came was brought to its culmination in his suffering. Just as John takes a different meaning from Caiaphas's words than meant by Caiaphas himself (John 11:47-52), so we can see that the purpose of Pilate bringing forth Jesus to the crowd as quite different than the purpose of God, who as on Mt. Sinai to Moses was making "all my goodness" pass before his people in the glorified Son of Man, the Word become flesh.

¹⁷ See my paper, "Creation or Redemption: When Did God Defeat Rahab/Leviathan?" (presented at the Annual Convention of the Evangelical Theological Society, November 20, 2013; https://www.academia.edu/7783524/Creation_or_Redemption_When_Did_God_Defeat_Rahab_Leviathan) as well as my dissertation referenced in n. 6, esp. chap. 5, 220-51.

¹⁸ *Frg. Tg. P* Exod 33:23; "You will see the Word (*dybwr*) of the Lord;" *Frg. Tg. V* and *Tg. Neof.*; "you will see the Word (*dbyr* / *dbwrh*) of the glory-of my Shekinah."